

TWINNED
By Stars

**DELIVERABLE D3.3 – REPORT ON THE PRODUCT DEVELOPED
INCLUDING A MARKETING & BUSINESS PLAN**

TWINNEDBYSTARS

UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND
DIGITALISATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED
ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES, AND

GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101124900

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CO	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
CAC	Customer acquisition cost
LTV	Lifetime value
ORs	Outermost Regions
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
MVP	Minimum viable product
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
CRM	Customer relationships management
NPS	Net Promoter Score
UGC	User generated content
UVP	Unique value proposition
OTA's	Online travel agencies
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
MICE	Meetings, Incentives, Conferences and Exhibitions
IAC	Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias
MOOCs	Massive Open Online Courses
WP	Work Package
KPIs	Key performance indicator
B2B	Business to business

1. INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

The organization of the four co-creation workshops, across the project's outermost regions (Canary Islands – Madeira – Azores – Martinique) led to the development of various business ideas proposed by the participating companies.

All the resulting ideas were subjected to a vote by the TWINNEDbySTARS community, with the aim of selecting one or more business proposals to be supported through to the end of the project.

Aligned with the overall project's values and goals, a set of evaluation criteria was defined, which included market potential, level of innovation, reduction of GHG emissions, digitalization, social responsibility, regional reach, and interest. A [survey](#) was distributed among stakeholders in the four regions, activating an online voting system during three months. These criteria were used by a total of 44 participating companies and stakeholders in the voting process:

Source: Own elaboration, information from co-creation workshops

After that evaluation by the TWINNEDbySTARS community, two products emerged as leaders throughout the co-creation process, ultimately achieving the highest overall scores:

- **Product 1:** Atlantic Starlight Adventure, a portal aggregating astrotourism experiences in the four outermost regions. This product received a rating of 3.69 / 5 and would be purchased by 59% of respondents.
- **Product 2:** Atlantic On-board Internships, a specialized multi-destination platform offering internships and student exchanges (from 1 week to 3 months) in the four Atlantic regions. with a rating of 3.74 / 5 and a purchase intention of 54%.

More info can be found in the project's [third newsletter](#)

Considering the close scores both products achieved (3.69 vs. 3.74) and strong support for both proposals (59% vs. 54%), the project decided to proceed with the development and accompaniment of both products.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THIS DOCUMENT

The objectives of this business plan are as follows:

1. Define the two selected products in their initial phase to achieve market launch. That is, to outline all the components required to bring the products to market and turn them into reality.
2. Establish a clear and structured go-to-market strategy to allow TWINNEDbySTARS to support both products (defined in section 3.1.9)
3. List all necessary resources and provide a financial estimate for launching the two products.
4. Set the short- and long-term goals that both products should achieve.

Therefore, this business plan outlines the various preparatory actions that will be undertaken throughout the duration of the project to ensure that both products continue to operate successfully after the project's conclusion.

Importantly, the proposed model is based on the development of an MVP (Minimum Viable Product), which is expected to undergo iterations, changes, and improvements based on feedback from real customers.

All changes and improvements that may arise during the upcoming months and until the end of the project will be included within an improved business plan version set to be created in month 35 following the project's roadmap.

Therefore, this document also includes a testing and validation model to incorporate such feedback into product development.

3. ATLANTIC STARLIGHT ADVENTURE

3.1 BUSINESS PLAN COMPONENTS

The following business plan is structurally defined using the **Business Model Canvas**, the same framework employed during the co-creation workshops to develop the business idea.

3.1.1 VALUE PROPOSITION

The core value proposition of *Atlantic Starlight Adventure* lies in the development of a specialized, multi-destination web platform featuring experiences that combine sailing and astrotourism in the four ORs (Outermost Regions).

This value proposition cannot be understood without first locating the current growth of astrotourism and ecotourism as a whole:

- **Market value:** In 2023, the global astrotourism market was valued at approximately \$250 million and is projected to reach \$400 million by 2030, ¹.
- **Consumer interest:** A 2025 survey by Booking.com indicated that 62% of travelers are considering visiting dark sky destinations for “starbathing” experiences.
- Analyzing **ecotourism** as a whole, and according to a report by Allied Market Research (2023), the global ecotourism market was valued at USD 185.2 billion in 2021, and is projected to reach over USD 520 billion by 2030, growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 14.3% during the period 2022-2030. Besides, 81% of global travelers say sustainability is important to them, and 50% would be willing to pay more for environmentally responsible services

The platform leverages three key elements:

1. The capitalization of a highly innovative and emerging industry: astrotourism.
2. The aggregation of all local offerings, which fosters growth by unifying the efforts of currently fragmented providers, who will improve and lengthen their service catalogue after including astrotourism experiences based on the TWINNEDbySTARS standards and guidelines
3. The portal's quality seal or guarantee offered to the final user, by only incorporating pre-approved experiences from companies with certified Starlight guides and validated itineraries and operations

¹ CAGR, 2023

The product also upholds the following environmental and functional values, which also set the foundations for participating companies when creating their astrotourism experiences:

- Protection of biodiversity and natural life cycles (e.g., bird species)
- Advocacy for dark skies. Participating companies are certified by the Starlight Foundation and adhere to the Declaration of La Palma.
- Prioritization of traditional sailing over motorized vessels, minimizing the use of combustion engines and associated pollution.
- Waste reduction and zero use of single-use plastics.
- Onboard waste sorting.
- No disposal of food into the sea.
- Onboard ashtrays.
- Social distancing protocols during combined whale watching activities (if applicable) in order to respect whales and other sea animals in their natural habitat

Additionally, the product offers strong social value:

- Raising awareness about light pollution (dark skies protection) and its negative impact on navigation and the environment.
- An alternative and engaging means to preserve traditional sailing and astronomy practices.
- Integration of scientific knowledge into recreational activities.
- Engagement of various population segments (e.g., schools) with the maritime environment.

3.1.2 KEY ACTIVITIES

To create the platform and deliver the planned products that the portal will market, the following key activities will be carried out:

- **Implementation program** for each participating company, focused on training and certifications. This aims to standardize quality by certifying skippers as Starlight guides and offering tailored training courses to ensure companies can provide high-quality, satisfying experiences
- Go-to-market and marketing strategy support provided by TWINNEDbySTARS
- Organization of a key astrotourism activity during each outing
- **Consulting support** for designing the experiences included in the portal in terms of timeline, duration, and activity combination.

- Commercialization of each product by each of the platform members through their own channels (inclusion of the product in their own websites, marketing through their own social media channels, etc.); following the agreement reached between all participating companies (see ANNEX 1).

3.1.3 CUSTOMER SEGMENTS / TARGET AUDIENCE

The initial go-to-market strategy will target the following customer segments:

- International tourists visiting any of the four outermost regions, often booking locally.
Within this group:
 - Tourists from continental Spain, Portugal, and France (languages as a connecting factor).
 - Tourists from other global markets.
- Sailors or sea enthusiasts looking to explore astrotourism.
- Non-sailing "adventurous" individuals seeking novel experiences.
- Astronomy enthusiasts eager to discover the stars from a new perspective (the sea).

Common targeting characteristics among these groups (to be tested):

- Age: 45–65 years.
- Preference for a relaxed lifestyle and a fascination with nature.
- Many are families with children aged 10–12 or older.

One goal during this launch phase is to identify which segment demonstrates the strongest product-market fit to refine targeting and communication strategies, and to optimize long-term scaling efforts.

3.1.4 KEY RESOURCES

To launch, maintain, and scale the platform, the following resources are required:

- Technological infrastructure: portal development (frontend, backend, server)
- Basic branding (color palette, logo, minimal visual identity)
- Initial audiovisual materials (photos, testimonials, teaser/trailer video)
- Online and offline advertising (social media, SEO, trade fairs, third-party intermediaries)
- Onboard materials (laser pointer, ancient navigation instruments, planispheres, etc.)

- Land-based astronomy-observation tools (telescopes, astrophotography equipment, etc.).
- Certified vessels and skippers trained through the program, or subcontracted astronomy professionals.

Notably, there is a shortage of professionals with both sailing and astrotourism expertise, complicating recruitment for experience delivery; hence, this factor will be considered as a potential threat that requires strengthening the training component of the platform for the offer side; and also reach specific partnerships to offset this effect (as stated in the next section)

3.1.5 KEY PARTNERS

- **Astronomical associations in the four Outermost Regions (ORs)**, along with key partners involved in the TWINNEDbySTARS Starlight Guide Program, include
 - The Astronomical Association of Madeira, for training support in Madeira's outings
 - The University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), a key alliance as an agent organizing and issuing the training certification after completing the TWINNEDbySTARS Starlight Guide Program
 - Agrupación Astronómica de Sabadell, institution that also certifies the course
 - Polaris Menorca and its trainer Javier Ares (Starlight Guide Program instructor)
 - Elena Ramos, light pollution expert (Starlight Guide Program instructor)
 - Naty Sánchez, mythology expert (Starlight Guide Program instructor)
- The **Starlight Foundation**, part of the Canary Islands Astrophysics Institute (IAC), a key partner for region, guide, and company certifications
- **Certified Starlight guides** and astronomical associations in each region when the participating companies cannot train their own staff members
- Local marinas.
- **Accommodation partners** for bundled experience packages.
- **Portal members** (strategic partners for multi-day inter-regional experiences).
- **Land-based activity partners** (to solve weather contingencies or experience enhancements)

3.1.6 CHANNELS

- **Platform website** with centralized customer support (managed by Nautic Ocean)
- Platform's social media profiles.
- Product pages on member companies' websites.
- Word of mouth and a **referral system**
- **Partnerships** with key associates in each of the 4 ORs (e.g., Discover Faial)
- Potential collaboration with **agencies**.

3.1.7 COST STRUCTURE

Two major cost areas exist:

1. Portal development and maintenance
2. Advertising and marketing

These costs can be specified as follows:

- Portal maintenance (server, hosting)
- Marketing campaigns to generate leads and bookings
- Social media management
- Lead handling and closing costs (sales personnel)
- Operational costs of boat outings (fuel, mooring, skipper)
- Starlight guide fees
- Integration of products on member websites
- Intensive implementation program (initial phase covered by TWINNEDbySTARS)

A sample Profit & Loss statement per outing is outlined below:

Concept	€ per outing
Gross income (fixed price)	90 €/person
20% portal commission	-18 €
Local provider revenue	72 €
Skipper	-30 €
Onboard materials	-5 €
Starlight guide cost	-10 €
Local provider margin	27 € per person

Source: Own elaboration based on outing forecast and industry numbers

Besides, an estimation of the launching plus maintenance costs of the platform has been outlined below:

Estimated Launch-to-Market Costs – Atlantic Starlight Adventure

Cost Category	Covered By	Notes and Estimated Value
Web platform development and hosting	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	Covered during launch: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2500€ website development • 50€ website domain • 150€ website server and hosting (one year) • 200€ required plugin licenses Ongoing maintenance funded via platform commissions (domain renewal + web server + plugin licenses)
SEO	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	On-page SEO for the whole site + product pages + blog content creation 1000€
Visual branding (logo, color palette, typography)	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	500 €
Social media creation (Facebook + Instagram + Youtube + TikTok)	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	500 €
Online advertising and visibility campaigns	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	Initial demand generation covered via Meta and Google
Company certification (Starlight Seal)	Participating companies	Mandatory for participation and joining the platform; 200€ per company/first year, then 100€ each renewed year
Guide certification (Starlight Guide Program)	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	Includes SEA STARLIGHT online course + practical session; fully covered
Company training program (quality standards, experience design)	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	Part of the intensive implementation program
Onboard educational materials (planispheres, laser pointers, etc.)	Participating companies	Required for activity execution; estimated €100–€300 per vessel (one-time payment)
Platform administration and operational management	Nautic Ocean (via 20% commission)	Commission breakdown: 5% for platform maintenance + improvement and marketing costs; 15% for operations

Source: Own elaboration based on estimates, this numbers are subject to change

3.1.8 REVENUE STREAMS

Overall, the business initiative will be materialized under 2 main highways:

1. Through the specialized platform described in this document
2. Within the particular websites of each of the platform members (that is, companies providing astronomical tourism products), who will be able to commercialize their own products through their own channels, as long as they comply with the agreements reached with the platform and other participating companies (especially when it comes to product pricing). Those agreements can be found in ANNEX 1

Hence, this business plan just focuses on the revenue streams forecasted for point 1 (the platform), and will exclude those owned by the platform's members.

The platform foresees 3 main revenue streams:

- Fixed-price product sales via the platform (standardized prices, independent from provider rates)
- 20% commission reinvested in demand generation and portal maintenance
- Intensive implementation program (post-project phase)

Long-term revenue strategies include:

- Development of intensive training programs to onboard new companies, covering skipper training, certification guidance, and communication skills.
- Monthly fees to boost visibility through promotional campaigns, using a shared budget

3.1.9 DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGY

The digital marketing strategy for the initial launching phase of *Atlantic Starlight Adventure* is designed to drive visibility, qualified traffic, and conversions through a comprehensive acquisition funnel approach:

Source: Own elaboration

It integrates both organic and paid initiatives, and partnerships, ensuring scalability and cost efficiency.

3.1.9.1 SEARCH ENGINE OPTIMIZATION (SEO) AND ORGANIC CONTENT

- **Thematic Blog:** With the creation of the platform/website, the creation of a blog will also take place. This blog will be filled with both evergreen and seasonal content focused on astrotourism, traditional sailing, sustainability, and regional guides to attract high-intent organic traffic.
- **On-page Optimization.** Apart from the blog, the plan is to implement advanced SEO techniques on all product pages, leveraging the power of a shared portal for more relevance, and trying to rank for local transactional searches.

- **Strategic Linkbuilding.** In order to gain those rankings, the project will work on the acquisition of backlinks from authoritative travel blogs, astronomy websites, key partners, and sustainable tourism platforms to enhance domain authority.

3.1.9.2. PAID MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

As SEO efforts will start to yield their benefits some months after the creation of the platform, the initial push of qualified traffic will come from paid marketing campaigns.

- Meta Ads (Facebook/Instagram):
 - *Top of Funnel:* Awareness campaigns utilizing high-impact visuals and short videos to generate interest among new audiences
 - *Middle & Bottom of Funnel:* Retargeting campaigns for website visitors, unconverted leads, and social media followers.
- Google Ads:
 - *Search Ads:* Targeted towards transactional keywords (e.g., “astrotourism in Madeira”, “night sailing Azores”).
 - *Display & Discovery:* Audience-based targeting focused on interests such as astronomy, eco-travel, and experiential tourism.
- **Creative A/B Testing:** Ongoing testing of messaging angles (astronomy, nature, sustainability, sailing) to determine optimal performance.

3.1.9.3 SOCIAL MEDIA STRATEGY

The creation of the different social media profiles for the project will also work as a cornerstone pillar. This will include two main content categories:

- **Organic Content:** Regular posting on Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube Shorts highlighting real experiences, customer testimonials, and educational content related to astronomy and navigation.
- **User-Generated Content (UGC):** Encouragement of participant posts through official hashtags, photo contests, or giveaways.

3.1.9.4. RETENTION AND REFERRAL STRATEGY

A referral system will be created to increase customer lifetime value:

- **Referral Program:** Incentivized sharing mechanism for customers who refer new users to the platform.
- **Loyalty Tactics:** Repeat customer bonuses, complimentary upgrades, or exclusive content for past participants.

3.1.9.5 CONVERSION OPTIMIZATION TACTICS

Finally, in order to improve conversion rate and closing rates throughout all stages, the following 2 tactics will be applied among all marketing channels:

- **Social Proof Mechanisms:** Verified reviews, testimonials, and average ratings are displayed prominently on product pages, which will be an essential element due to the newness of the product
- **Trust Signals:** Emphasis on experience certification, flexible cancellation policies, and safety standards to reduce booking hesitation.

3.2 TESTING FRAMEWORK

One of the primary objectives of this business plan is to clearly define a testing framework that enables the incorporation of tangible improvements into the product, thereby transforming the launched Minimum Viable Product (MVP) into a fully validated solution endorsed by the market.

To achieve this, mechanisms will be established to collect feedback from both potential and actual customers, as well as to explore different iterations regarding the types of experiences offered through the platform:

Source: Own elaboration

As illustrated in the diagram above, the methodology for this iterative process and testing cycle is structured in the following phases:

3.2.1 PHASE 1: PRODUCT DEPLOYMENT PER REGION

Initially, various products will be launched on the platform in each of the four Outermost Regions (ORs). These offerings will be promoted through the marketing and advertising strategies previously outlined, in order to attract potential clients.

3.2.2 PHASE 2: REGIONAL CUSTOMIZATION AND TESTING

Due to the potential regional differences among the four ORs, as well as variations in local demand preferences and composition, diverse product formats will be tested to identify the most effective configuration for each region.

Specifically, the following elements will be subject to experimentation:

- Planning and scheduling of each outing
- Integration of land-based activities (e.g., telescope sessions) aligned with the maritime experience
- Duration of each segment of the outing
- Contingency plans and guarantees in case of adverse weather conditions
- Additional features and services (e.g., catering)

3.2.3 PHASE 3: SALES PROCESS AS FIRST FEEDBACK POINT

The commercial and sales process will serve as the initial point of contact and feedback collection. One major advantage of centralizing all experiences under a single platform is the ability to consolidate customer service and sales through a single entity (in this case, Nautic Ocean). This will facilitate:

1. Identifying the main objections to booking the experience (thereby enabling the adjustment of the value proposition and implementation of assurance mechanisms)
2. Defining frequently asked questions (which can then be addressed in individual product pages)
3. Understanding key purchasing drivers and the aspects of the value proposition most valued by customers (to amplify them in communication and advertising efforts)

3.2.4 PHASE 4: POST-EXPERIENCE FEEDBACK COLLECTION

After the booking and completion of the experience, individual follow-up calls will be conducted with participating clients to gather specific feedback. The aim is to return to the initial planning phase and refine the product accordingly.

This process will identify:

- The most highly valued elements of the outing
- Elements that can be removed due to low perceived value, to improve operational efficiency and margins
- Additional features or experiences clients would have liked to see included

3.3 PHASED GO-TO-MARKET STRATEGY (APRIL 2025 – OCTOBER 2026)

3.3.1 PHASE 1 – PREPARATION (APRIL–JUNE 2025)

- Fully define the Unique Selling Proposition and all required marketing messages and market positioning, including brand values
- Web development (via external provider) and portal launch
- Creation of visual identity and drafting of website content
- Coordination with local providers for the development of experiences to be included on the portal
- Training program for companies and coordination with key partners (e.g., certified astronomy guides)
- Creation of social media profiles

3.3.2 PHASE 2 – LAUNCH (JULY–OCTOBER 2025)

- Platform goes live with experiences in all 4 regions (at least one per region)
- Organic outreach through blog articles and SEO optimization of transactional product pages
- Meta Ads campaigns for lead generation
- Testing of leads / objections / refinement of value proposition
- First round of post-experience user feedback
- CRM (customer relationship management software) tracking to monitor conversion rate from web contact to booking
- A/B testing on social media using different messaging angles (astronomy, nature, sailing, etc.)
- Price strategy testing

3.3.3 PHASE 3 – SCALING (2026)

- Increase the number of experiences per region
- Consolidate provider network and conduct additional training to enhance existing offerings
- Optimize SEO for international audiences
- Activate referral system
- Evaluate the implementation of online payment and booking systems if volume justifies it
- Conduct structured post-outing surveys (online and via phone)
- Develop an internal dashboard to track objections, leads, and conversion rates by product type

3.4 EXPECTED IMPACTS / KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

The following outlines the short-term objectives and expected impacts of the go-to-market strategy until the project concludes, as well as long-term projections post-project completion:

3.4.1 EXPECTED IMPACTS DURING THE PROJECT (APRIL 2025 – OCTOBER 2026)

- Launch of 2 to 3 distinct products (delivered by different companies) in each of the four project regions
- Execution of a minimum of 2 outings per product/destination (forecasted number. The goal is subject to change depending on market response)
- Generation of 5 leads per month per region
- Lead-to-booking conversion rate of 5%

Additional performance indicators:

- Growth in social media followers: achieve at least 300 followers on Instagram and Facebook
- Website traffic: generate at least 500 website visits per month
- Client satisfaction based on survey results (Net Promoter Score): Average experience rating of 7 or above)

3.4.2 LONG-TERM IMPACTS: POST-PROJECT (BEYOND OCTOBER 2026)

Overall, after the conclusion of the project and its accompaniment, the project aims to achieve the following overarching goals beyond 2026:

- Sustained operation and growth of the platform through validated product-market fit
- Ongoing lead generation and experience bookings
- Continuous optimization of offerings based on user feedback
- Financial self-sufficiency of the portal through commissions and reinvestment in demand generation
- Net promoter score of 9 or 10

And, in order to achieve those goals, these are the lines of work to be carried out during the scaling phase:

3.4.2.1 WORK ON SCALABLE UNIT ECONOMICS

The following KPIs must be achieved for long-term profitability success:

KPI	Formula	GOAL
CAC (Customer Acquisition Cost)	Marketing Spend / N° clients acquired	≤ 25 €
LTV (Customer Lifetime Value)	Average ticket × frequency × margin	120 €
LTV / CAC Ratio	LTV / CAC	≥ 3

Source: Own elaboration

And in order to achieve those metrics, the following tactics must be implemented:

- Incentivize repetition (packs, bonuses, referrals)
- Reduce CAC via SEO/automation.
- Increase average ticket with upselling (premium astrophoto, catering, etc.).

3.4.2.2 AUTOMATE THE CUSTOMER JOURNEY TO SCALE WITHOUT INCREASING STAFF

In order to reduce structural costs and keep scaling the platform, one of the long-term goals of the platform will be improving the acquisition funnel as follows:

- **Awareness:** International SEO, value content on astrotourism on social media (video format: YouTube shorts, TikTok & Instagram reels); plus guest posts in specialized platforms
- **Acquisition:** Generation of lead magnets to capture more leads on the upper stages of the sales funnel (for example, checklist to see stars, “best seasons” guide, etc.)
- **Nurturing:** Automated email flows through email marketing software to nurture the leads acquired in the prior step
- **Conversion:** Synced calendar booking system + online payment integrated into the platform

3.4.2.3 EXPAND NETWORK COLLABORATIONS ONCE THE PRODUCT HAS BEEN VALIDATED:

Besides the online marketing actions mentioned in the prior section, offline actions to expand collaborations should also be carried out, harnessing the strength of already-established stakeholders:

- **Specialized OTAs:** For example, Responsible Travel, Much Better Adventures, Ecobnb.
- **Dark sky tourism portals**
- **Educational booking platforms**, like ClassGap, ErasmusIntern, Workaway.
- **Niche cruise lines or slow tourism:** alliances with small shipping companies.
- **Experiential Tourism Platforms**, e.g., *Evaneos*, *Bookatrekking*, *MuchBetterAdventures* through API or catalog integration; standard commission %
- **European Universities** like *Erasmus+*, *biology or astrophysics faculties*, Accredited internship programs; achieving a visibility goal + ESG impact
- **Scientific NGOs**, offering the fleet as a floating lab and achieving win-win collaboration packages
- **B2B MICE Agencies.** Astrotourism for teambuilding activities. Exclusive corporate product

3.4.2.4 GROWTH IN ADDITIONAL MARKET SEGMENTS

Once the product achieves product market fit and the initial customer segments defined within this business plan have been validated, the platform can aim to expand and target extra customer groups, which constitute smaller niches, like the following:

Vertical	Offer	Target customer
Astrophotography	Outings with a professional photographer + editing workshop	Amateur photographers, tech lovers
Scientific Expeditions	Sailing + marine data collection	STEM students, NGOs, scientific volunteers
Blue Wellness	Sunset yoga + stargazing	Women aged 35–55, eco-wellness segment
Whale & Sky	Whale watching + stargazing	Families, eco-adventurers

Source: Own elaboration

4. ATLANTIC ON-BOARD INTERNSHIPS

4.1 BUSINESS PLAN COMPONENTS

Again, the following business plan for the Atlantic On-Board Internships product is structurally defined using the **Business Model Canvas**, which helped guide the co-creation of this product within the project's workshops:

4.1.1 VALUE PROPOSITION

Atlantic ON-BOARD Internships is a specialized multi-destination platform offering student internships and exchange opportunities (ranging from 1 week to 3 months) across the four Atlantic regions.

The portal provides a transformative learning experience at sea for students, researchers, and enthusiasts of scientific tourism.

It combines and offers participants as a core value offering:

- Practical and theoretical training in navigation, marine biology, and scientific techniques.
- Cultural immersion in unique Atlantic regions (Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands, Martinique).
- An ecosystem of companies committed to sustainability and social responsibility, and the resulting direct collaboration between them
- A flexible, modular program structure tailored to different academic or personal development needs

Unique Value Proposition (UVP):

"We help European students and universities access impactful maritime internships in the Atlantic, removing barriers related to logistics, quality, and administration."

Societal and Environmental Impact:

- Stimulates scientific and maritime vocations in youth.
- Expands access to practical training in outermost regions
- Supports ocean protection through science-based education.
- Promotes sustainable navigation aligned with SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) and the Blue Economy agenda.

4.1.2 KEY CUSTOMER SEGMENTS

Key customer segments for this product include:

- European universities and educational institutions (undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs).
- Young Europeans on gap years and Erasmus+ programs.
- Researchers in marine fields (biology, climatology, acoustics).
- Volunteer tourists and marine/whale enthusiasts.
- Scientific or nature photographers.
- NGOs and organizations promoting sustainable educational practices

Again, the goal of the initial launch phase of the product is to test and understand which segments yield better traction with the product so that required iterations can be implemented based on that conclusion.

MARKET CONTEXT & TRENDS

The potential of this portal, as well as the fit with the aforementioned market segments, relies on the following market trends:

- ~73.6M young Europeans consider gap-year travel²
- 43% of EU adults aged 25–34 hold a tertiary degree³
- 4–6M internships/year in the EU; 50% of citizens aged 15–35 have completed one⁴
- Adventure tourism represented 35% of the European market in 2022⁵

4.1.3 CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS

The relation with the different market segments and buyer personas will be carried out under the following parameters:

- **Automated + Assisted:** Creation of a platform, including an FAQ section and human support for complex inquiries

² CBI - Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2024 - <https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/tourism/gap-year-tourism/market-potential?>

³ Eurstat, 2023 - https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Educational_attainment_statistics

⁴ European Court of Auditors - https://www.eca.europa.eu/ECAPublications/RV-2024-01/RV-2024-01_EN.pdf

⁵ GlobeNewswire, 2022 - <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2022/08/05/2493138/0/en/Global-Adventure-Tourism-Industry-worth-Over-3-5th-contribution-by-Soft-Tourism-Future-Market-Insights-Inc.html>

- **Community:** Newsletters, closed alumni groups, and ongoing engagement via social media.
- **Personalized Mentorship:** Support before, during, and after the internship.

4.1.4 DISTRIBUTION CHANNELS

In order to reach and attract demand, the following channels will be used:

- Multi-destination web portal managed by the consortium during the initial launching phase, and after the end of the project by Biosean, one of the participating companies
- Websites of participating companies
- Universities and Erasmus+ platforms
- Social media and scientific tourism channels
- Presence at environmental and educational fairs in Europe.

4.1.5 KEY RESOURCES

The following resources will become essential for the development and launch of the project:

- Network of partner nautical and scientific companies.
- Booking platform and multilingual CRM (long-term).
- Logistical infrastructure (accommodation, transport, catering)
- Research equipment (hydrophones, cameras, etc.).
- Human resources: tutors, skippers, scientists, and community managers.

4.1.6 KEY ACTIVITIES

The aforementioned list of resources will be put to use to develop the following activities, which will also be essential for the long-term maintenance and success of the project:

- Development and maintenance of the online platform
- Establishment of agreements with universities and scholarship programs
- Co-design of training itineraries with local companies
- Logistical coordination of internships
- Digital marketing and scientific content strategy
- Quality assurance and compliance with environmental protocols

4.1.7 KEY PARTNERS

In order to start with the business operations, the following partners will become key alliances:

- Nautical companies from Madeira, Azores, Canary Islands, and Martinique.
- Universities (ULPGC and the European university network).
- Environmental NGOs.
- Companies such as CIRCE (Conservación, Información y Estudio sobre cetáceos) Regional institutions and Erasmus+ programs.
- TWINNEDbySTARS (strategic support and visibility)
- Student associations like International [Students Life Las Palmas Association](#)

4.1.8 COST STRUCTURE

In assessing the overall cost structure the project must face, we can list the following items:

- Personnel costs (coordination, tutors, customer support).
- Web design and maintenance expenses
- Production of training materials.
- Operational costs per stay (transport, meals, insurance).
- Investment in marketing (especially digital) and visibility/outreach
- Administrative and financial costs/overheads

Estimated Launch-to-Market Costs – Atlantic On-Board Internships

Cost Category	Covered By	Notes and Estimated Value
Web platform development and hosting	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	Covered during launch: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2500€ website development • 50€ website domain • 100€ website server and hosting (one year) • 200€ required plugin licenses Ongoing maintenance funded via platform commissions (domain renewal + web server + plugin licenses)
SEO	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	On-page SEO 1000€
Visual branding (logo, color palette, typography)	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	500 €
Social media creation (Instagram, Facebook, Youtube, TikTok)	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	500 €
Online advertising and visibility campaigns	TWINNEDbySTARS Project	Initial demand generation covered via Meta and Google
Scientific equipment for onboard training (e.g., hydrophones)	Participating companies	Variable cost depending on each company's strategy (estimated 100 - 500€)
Platform administration and maintenance	Biosean (via 5% commission)	Covers technical upkeep and digital marketing; deducted per booking

Source: Own elaboration based on estimates, this numbers are subject to change

4.1.9 REVENUE STREAMS

And the sources of revenue that will sustain the platform and generate profitability per participating companies:

- Direct sale of internships (1-week to 3-month packages).
- Commission-based agreements with partner universities.
- Revenue from scientific content (future MOOCs, webinars).
- Potential sponsorships or collaborations with aligned brands.
- Erasmus+ grants, youth, and environmental programs.

4.2 KPIS AND OBJECTIVES

Next, we can find an outline of the short-term goals set for the project during the initial launching phase (that is, during the accompaniment from TWINNEDbySTARS), as well as after the project comes to an end (from 2026 onward)

4.2.1 SHORT-TERM (THROUGH OCTOBER 2026)

Initial MVP Scope:

- 1 fully operational internship per region (at least 3)
- 3 pilot partner universities
- 10–20 student participants
- Manual logistics (low-tech backend) to prioritize learning and validation.
- Functional web platform launched before June 2025
- Creation of social media channels (Facebook, Instagram, Youtube, TikTok)

Success Criteria:

- Establishment of a feedback and follow-up system post-internship, with an Net Promoter Score (NPS) among participants of 7 or higher $NPS \geq 7$
- Conversion rate $> 5\%$ from sign-ups.
- 2 repeat collaborations with universities
- Operational alliance among at least 5 regional companies
- At least 300 followers on Social Media
- At least 300 monthly visits to the website / platform
- At least 6 partnership agreements with European universities

4.2.2 LONG-TERM (2026 ONWARD)

Once the launch phase is complete, the following are the goals the project sets to achieve in the long run:

Vision: To become the leading European platform for maritime internships in the Atlantic

- Become the benchmark for marine internships in Atlantic regions.
- Consolidate a community of 500+ alumni per year.
- Achieve sustainable profitability with reinvestment in green innovation.
- Maintain common environmental protocols and certification of best practices across the network.

4.3 TESTING & PRODUCT ITERATION

In order to launch the project, the following actions will be carried out to support everything mentioned so far in order to get the required feedback for product iteration:

4.3.1 PROBLEM VALIDATION

As stated above within the customer segments section, preliminary research supports market opportunity, but deeper problem-solution validation will be carried out to gain a better understanding of the iterations required to achieve product-market fit:

Key Pain Points to Validate:

- Lack of ocean-based, hands-on learning for marine studies.
- Fragmentation and opacity in internship logistics across Atlantic regions.
- Scarcity of trusted, sustainable, and academically recognized internship programs.

Validation Actions:

- Interviews with Erasmus+ coordinators, university administrators, and students (15–30).
- Piloting short-term internships with structured feedback.
- Landing page to measure interest via sign-ups.

4.3.2 TESTING & LEARNING ROADMAP

A structured testing loop will guide iterations:

1. **Problem interviews** to validate real pains and willingness to pay.
2. **Landing page + sign-ups** to measure early traction and segment interest.
3. **Pilot internships** to collect structured feedback + evaluate NPS.
4. **A/B messaging tests** to optimize conversion on different claims (science vs. adventure).
5. **University collaboration feedback** to adjust B2B process and academic value proposition

5. ANNEX 1: COLLABORATION AGREEMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND LAUNCHING OF “ATLANTIC STARLIGHT ADVENTURE”, A TOURIST PRODUCT OF ASTROTOURISM AND SAILING IN MADEIRA - CANARY ISLANDS - AZORES - MARTINICA.

The following is the draft of the cooperation agreement currently under development, which will be signed during the first phase of the Atlantic Starlight Adventure platform’s development.

The agreement will initially be signed by the following companies, which confirmed their participation during the various co-creation workshops

- La Pirogue Kalina in Martinique
- Keep Sailing and Nautic Ocean in the Canary Islands
- Happy Hour, Madeira Sunkiss Sailing and Madeira Boat Rentals in Madeira
- Naturalist in Azores

In xxxxx, on the xx of xxxxxx, 2025.

This document constitutes a specific agreement established to lay out the general framework for maintaining the cooperation between the project partners and collaborating companies involved in the Atlantic Starlight Adventure product, developed under the European project ‘TWINNEDbySTARS – Unleashing the Potential of Innovation, Circularity and Digitalisation to Accelerate New Marine Ecotourism, Joint Practices and Businesses in the Outermost Regions (ORs)’, funded by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (project number: 101124900).

GATHERED

On one side, Mr/Ms xxxxxxxxxxxx, Sole Administrator/Manager of the company xxxxx, with tax identification number (C.I.F.) xxxxxxxx and registered address at xxxxxxxxxxxxxx. Corporate purpose: xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx.

On the other side, Mr/Ms xxxxxxxxxxxx, Sole Administrator/Manager of the company xxxxx, with tax identification number (C.I.F.) xxxxxxxx and registered address at xxxxxxxxxxxxxx. Corporate purpose: xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx.

On the other side, Mr/Ms xxxxxxxxxxxx, Sole Administrator/Manager of the company xxxxx, with tax identification number (C.I.F.) xxxxxxxx and registered address at xxxxxxxxxxxxxx. Corporate purpose: xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx.

On the other side, Mr/Ms xxxxxxxxxxxx, Sole Administrator/Manager of the company xxxxx, with tax identification number (C.I.F.) xxxxxxxx and registered address at xxxxxxxxxxxxxx. Corporate purpose: xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx.

The parties mutually recognise their legal capacity to enter into this agreement, and accordingly,

DECLARE

That, in accordance with the outcomes of the Co-creation Workshops held in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Funchal, online for Martinique, and in Faial, and following the subsequent voting process, these entities have agreed to establish collaborative relations for the joint development of activities in the field of astrotourism and navigation.

That the parties wish to establish close cooperation with the aim of fostering the creation and commercialisation of the Atlantic Starlight Adventures platform and tourism product, which consists of developing nautical astrotourism routes in the regions of Madeira, the Canary Islands, the Azores, and Martinique. This form of tourism provides multiple benefits, including star observation, raising awareness of light pollution, marine biodiversity preservation, and the promotion of traditional navigation. Furthermore, the Starlight certification for nautical companies offers international recognition and visibility, positioning certified businesses within a growing astrotourism network.

It reinforces commitment to sustainability, supports tourism diversification, and attracts new visitor segments such as astronomy, photography, and scientific tourism enthusiasts. Operationally, it enables companies to distinguish themselves through certified experiences, offer night-time operations, and enhance the connection between navigation and celestial knowledge.

That the parties declare that Mr/Ms..... acts as an observer to ensure the proper development of the Agreement.

Based on the above, the parties express their intent to formalise this Specific Collaboration Agreement under the following

CLAUSES

FIRST – TWINNEDbySTARS PROJECT

The TWINNEDbySTARS project aims to position the EU's Outermost Regions as internationally recognised marine ecotourism destinations, leveraging tourism benefits for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation.

It builds on the success of previous initiatives in the Macaronesia region, which established networks and methodological frameworks for co-designing and optimising transformative marine ecotourism products and activities involving SMEs across different islands. Onboard environmental education, navigation, responsible marine wildlife observation, and the use of Starlight attributes are examples of best practices that, when combined with innovative interpretative experiences, have achieved high tourist satisfaction and promoted more responsible behaviour among SMEs and visitors. TWINNEDbySTARS seeks to scale these experiences across all EU ORs, encouraging green and digital innovation adoption, strengthening existing alliances, fostering capacity building, and creating co-creation opportunities.

Within its activities, the Atlantic Starlight Adventures product has been developed – a nautical astrotourism platform for maritime tourism companies in the four Outermost Regions of Madeira, Martinique, the Azores, and the Canary Islands. This joint platform will promote tourism aligned with ancestral navigation traditions, raising awareness of light pollution and its visual and environmental impact on marine and terrestrial species.

SECOND – PURPOSE OF THE AGREEMENT

This is a specific agreement with the concrete objective of establishing working guidelines among participating companies for the launch of the new tourism product Atlantic Starlight Adventures in the Outermost Regions of Madeira, the Azores, Martinique, and the Canary Islands. The nautical astrotourism routes will be offered via a joint digital platform, with each company retaining independence in pricing and services, ensuring that prices listed on the platform are not lower than those published on their own websites and adhering to quality and sustainability standards set forth in this agreement.

THIRD – PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT AND JOINT ACTION

The parties agree to develop and promote Atlantic Starlight Adventures through the following actions:

- Creation of a visual identity and promotional materials.
- Development of the joint digital platform.

FOURTH – COMMITMENT OF THE PARTIES

Nautic Ocean and ULPGC commit to providing mentorship and guidance during the initial astrotourism outings, supporting companies in integrating and consolidating this offering within their services. To this end, they will organise the SEA STARLIGHT training, consisting of 20 hours of online content and one practical outing per region.

Keep Sailing, Sunkiss Sailing, Biosean, and xxxxx commit to incorporating astrotourism outings in their commercial offer, using their standard sales channels and becoming part of the Atlantic Starlight Adventures platform by listing their outings on the website.

All signatory companies must meet the following minimum quality and sustainability requirements to participate in the platform:

- Adherence to agreed platform pricing.
- Onboard recycling and adoption of sustainable practices.
- Reduction of single-use plastics in all activities.
- Compliance with MARPOL regulations, ensuring proper marine waste management.
- Acquisition and annual renewal of the Starlight certification.
- Minimisation of light pollution during night-time activities.
- Completion of the SEA STARLIGHT training course to ensure the quality of the astrotourism experience.

The platform administrator, NAUTIC OCEAN, shall assume the following responsibilities:

- Management and maintenance of the website and social media channels.
- Supervision of participating companies' compliance with commitments.
- Coordination with certification entities to ensure certificate renewal.
- Product promotion and engagement with new companies interested in joining the initiative.

SIXTH – FUNDING

All actions described in this Agreement and dedicated to the product launch will be partially funded by the TWINNEDbySTARS Project, under its work plan 'WP3: Creation of new spaces for co-creating new products and nautical tourism experiences', specifically tasks '3.3: Product development, marketing, and business planning' and '3.4: Product testing'. These costs include:

- Website development
- Social media and SEO strategy
- Consultancy for experience creation and agreements with local astrotourism, astronomy, navigation, or local gastronomy providers

External funding after the conclusion of the TWINNEDbySTARS Project is not considered necessary, as the product is expected to be self-sustaining through customer revenue, which is the project's main objective.

The platform's maintenance will be funded via a percentage of revenue generated through bookings. Each participating company will contribute 5% of their sales on the platform for system management and updates. The full complete commission-cost scheme is detailed in the next section with further details.

SEVENTH – PRICING AND PRODUCT DIFFERENTIATION

Each signatory company agrees to offer its nautical astrotourism services on the Atlantic Starlight Adventures platform at the same price as published on its own official website, ensuring transparency for customers and fairness among all partners.

In cases where two or more companies operate in the same region, **direct competition between similar products shall be avoided**. Before launching any new product in such a region, participating companies shall collaborate—under the coordination of the platform manager, Nautic Ocean—to **ensure sufficient differentiation between offerings**.

This differentiation may include, but is not limited to:

- type of vessel (e.g., sailboat vs. catamaran)
- inclusion or exclusion of catering
- route duration or timing
- presence of land-based components
- or any other feature that creates a distinct experience for the end user.

The objective is to allow the platform to present clearly distinct options to potential clients, enhancing user choice without creating internal competition. All proposals for new experiences must undergo a prior review process coordinated by the platform manager to guarantee compliance with this differentiation principle.

In the event of multiple suitable offers within the same region, Nautic Ocean will present all validated options equally to the customer, without promoting one provider over another.

EIGHT – REVENUE SHARING, COMMISSIONS & PLATFORM REINVESTMENT

From each booking made through the platform, Nautic Ocean, as the agent marketing the different experiences, selling them, and maintaining the portal, will keep a 20% commission.

A 25% of this total commission (that is, a 5% from each booking value) will be dedicated to funding:

- Website hosting and maintenance
- Execution of promotional and online advertising strategies and campaigns to generate more clients
- Continuous SEO improvement of the platform

No party may use this 5% revenue share for purposes unrelated to the platform's enhancement.

The commission will be paid to Nautic Ocean after each individual booking is closed and paid by the client.

Besides, quarterly statements will be issued to each company, stating:

- Number of website visits to their product pages
- Number of leads generated for their products during the past quarter
- Number of bookings made through the platform

To maintain trust and positive relations among the signatories, periodic reviews may be conducted regarding commission implementation and results in terms of platform maintenance and promotion. Should discrepancies arise, the parties shall, in good faith, agree upon appropriate audit and control mechanisms.

Signing this Agreement implies acceptance of these commission terms, and any breach may constitute grounds for termination as specified in the relevant clause.

NINTH – DURATION OF THE AGREEMENT

This Agreement shall have an initial duration of one year, automatically renewable indefinitely. The Agreement will remain in force unless any signatory party formally withdraws, with notice given to the other parties at least one (1) month prior to the intended termination date.

TENTH – TERMINATION OF THE AGREEMENT

The activities covered by this agreement may be discontinued by mutual consent, either due to ineffectiveness of the platform or for any other reason.

Failure by any party to fulfil the obligations herein shall entitle the other parties to terminate the Agreement, with all rights regarding the subject matter of the work being automatically annulled.

ELEVENTH – JURISDICTION

Any disputes arising from the interpretation, development, modification, resolution, and effects of this Agreement, as well as specific agreements derived from it, shall be resolved by a Monitoring Committee to be established for that purpose. Should consensus not be reached, the parties, expressly waiving any other jurisdiction, agree to submit the matter to the Courts and Tribunals of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.

TWELVETH – COLLABORATION AMONG SIGNATORIES

The signatories agree to cooperate at all times in good faith and with efficiency to ensure the proper implementation of the agreed terms, and to foster and promote the cultural, scientific, and technological development of the institutions involved.

In witness whereof, and for all appropriate purposes, the parties sign this document in a single copy and tenor, on the date indicated in the heading.

6. ANNEX 2: COLLABORATION AGREEMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND LAUNCHING OF “ATLANTIC ON-BOARD INTERNSHIPS”, A TOURIST PRODUCT FOR ON-BOARD TRAINING IN MADEIRA - CANARY ISLANDS - AZORES - MARTINICA

Finally, the following cooperation agreement is currently being developed and will be signed during the first phase of the Atlantic On-board Internships platform and product development.

The agreement will initially be signed by the following companies, which confirmed their participation during the various co-creation workshops:

- Biosean and Nautic Ocean in the Canary Islands
- Seafret and Totem in Martinique
- MT Madeira and Madeira Sunkiss Sailing in Madeira
- Naturalist, Saildive and Diveazores in Azores

In xxxxx, on the xx of xxxxxx, 2025.

This document constitutes a specific agreement aimed at establishing the general framework for maintaining the cooperation between project partners and collaborating companies involved in the Atlantic On-board Internship product, developed under the European project ‘TWINNEDbySTARS – Unleashing the Potential of Innovation, Circularity and Digitalisation to Accelerate New Marine Ecotourism, Joint Practices and Businesses in the Outermost Regions (ORs)’, funded by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (project number: 101124900).

GATHERED

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The parties mutually recognise their legal capacity to enter into this agreement, and accordingly,

DECLARE

That, in accordance with the outcomes of the Co-creation Workshops held in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Funchal, online for Martinique, and in Faial, and following the subsequent voting process, these entities have agreed to establish collaborative relations for the joint implementation of onboard training activities.

That the parties wish to establish close cooperation with the aim of fostering the creation and commercialisation of the platform and tourism product "Atlantic On-board Internships", which involves the development of onboard training and internship activities in Madeira, the Canary Islands, the Azores, and Martinique. This educational form of tourism provides multiple benefits, as it promotes research and marine biodiversity conservation, creates learning and professional development opportunities for participants, and contributes to the sustainable development of local economies through the implementation of responsible and environmentally respectful practices.

Based on the above, the parties express their intent to formalise this Specific Collaboration Agreement under the following

CLAUSES

FIRST – TWINNEDbySTARS PROJECT

The TWINNEDbySTARS project aims to position the EU's Outermost Regions as internationally recognised marine ecotourism destinations, leveraging tourism benefits for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation.

It builds on the success of previous initiatives in the Macaronesia region, which established networks and methodological frameworks for co-designing and optimising transformative marine ecotourism products and activities involving SMEs across different islands.

Onboard environmental education, navigation, responsible marine wildlife observation, and the use of Starlight attributes are examples of best practices that, when combined with innovative interpretative experiences, have achieved high tourist satisfaction and promoted more responsible behaviour among SMEs and visitors. TWINNEDbySTARS seeks to scale these experiences across all EU ORs, encouraging green and digital innovation adoption, strengthening existing alliances, fostering capacity building, and creating co-creation opportunities.

Within its activities, the Atlantic On-board Internships product has been developed – a platform offering internships and onboard education for maritime tourism companies in the four Outermost Regions of Madeira, Martinique, the Azores, and the Canary Islands. This joint

platform will promote tourism aligned with the importance of science and hands-on learning, offering unique immersive experiences in the marine environment and local culture while reinforcing a commitment to sustainability and tourism excellence in these regions.

SECOND – PURPOSE OF THE AGREEMENT

This is a specific agreement with the concrete objective of establishing working guidelines among participating companies for the launch of the new tourism product Atlantic On-board Internships in the Outermost Regions of Madeira, the Azores, Martinique, and the Canary Islands. The onboard education internships will be offered via a joint digital platform, with each company retaining independence in pricing and services, ensuring that prices listed on the platform are not lower than those published on their own websites and adhering to quality and sustainability standards set forth in this agreement.

THIRD – PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT AND JOINT ACTION

The parties agree to develop and promote Atlantic On-board Internships through the following actions:

- Creation of a visual identity and promotional materials.
- Development of the joint digital platform.
- Marketing campaigns and participation in tourism fairs and events.
- Establishment of strategic alliances with institutions and sectoral entities.
- Setting and maintaining quality standards required for participation in the platform.

FOURTH – COMMITMENT OF THE PARTIES

Biosean commits to incorporating educational experiences and internships into its commercial offer, using its usual sales channels, and to participating in the Atlantic On-board Internships platform by listing its outings on the website.

Naturalist likewise commits to incorporating educational experiences and internships into its commercial offer, using its usual sales channels, and to participating in the Atlantic On-board Internships platform by listing its outings on the website.

All signatory companies must meet the following minimum quality and sustainability requirements to participate in the platform:

- Adherence to agreed platform pricing.
- Onboard recycling and adoption of sustainable practices.
- Reduction of single-use plastics in all activities.
- Compliance with MARPOL regulations, ensuring proper marine waste management.
- Minimisation of light pollution during night-time activities, where applicable.

The platform administrator, BIOSEAN, shall assume the following responsibilities:

- Management and maintenance of the website and social media channels.
- Supervision of participating companies' compliance with commitments.
- Product promotion and engagement with new companies interested in joining the initiative.

SIXTH – FUNDING

All actions described in this Agreement and dedicated to the product launch will be partially funded by the TWINNEDbySTARS Project, under its work plan 'WP3: Creation of new spaces for co-creating new products and nautical tourism experiences', specifically tasks '3.3: Product development, marketing, and business planning' and '3.4: Product testing'. These costs include:

- Website development
- Social media and SEO strategy

External funding after the conclusion of the TWINNEDbySTARS Project is not considered necessary, as the product is expected to be self-sustaining through customer revenue, which is the project's main objective. The platform's maintenance will be funded via a percentage of revenue generated through bookings. Each participating company will contribute x% of their sales on the platform for system management and updates.

SEVENTH – COMMISSIONS AND PLATFORM MAINTENANCE

Each signatory company commits to offering its onboard internship and educational services through the Atlantic On-board Internships platform at the same prices as listed on their own website, ensuring transparency for customers and fairness among partners.

To cover maintenance, technical updates, and SEO of the platform, a 5% commission on each booking made through the platform is established. This percentage will exclusively fund:

- Website hosting and maintenance
- Execution of promotional and online advertising strategies
- Continuous SEO improvement of the platform

The commission is calculated as 5% of the total value of each booking through the platform. For each booking, the difference will be deducted before payment is made to the company providing the service.

All commission income will be used solely for the platform's maintenance and improvement, including potential contracting of digital marketing and advertising services. No party may use this fund for purposes unrelated to the platform's enhancement.

To maintain trust and positive relations among the signatories, periodic reviews may be conducted regarding commission implementation and results in terms of platform maintenance and promotion. Should discrepancies arise, the parties shall, in good faith, agree upon appropriate audit and control mechanisms.

Signing this Agreement implies acceptance of these commission terms, and any breach may constitute grounds for termination as specified in the relevant clause.

EIGHTH – DURATION OF THE AGREEMENT

This Agreement shall have an initial duration of one year, automatically renewable indefinitely. The Agreement will remain in force unless any signatory party formally withdraws, with notice given to the other parties at least one (1) month prior to the intended termination date.

NINTH – TERMINATION OF THE AGREEMENT

The activities covered by this agreement may be discontinued by mutual consent, either due to ineffectiveness of the platform or for any other reason.

Failure by any party to fulfil the obligations herein shall entitle the other parties to terminate the Agreement, with all rights regarding the subject matter of the work being automatically annulled.

TENTH – JURISDICTION

Any disputes arising from the interpretation, development, modification, resolution, and effects of this Agreement, as well as specific agreements derived from it, shall be resolved by a Monitoring Committee to be established for that purpose. Should consensus not be reached, the parties, expressly waiving any other jurisdiction, agree to submit the matter to the Courts and Tribunals of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.

ELEVENTH – COLLABORATION AMONG SIGNATORIES

The signatories agree to cooperate at all times in good faith and with efficiency to ensure the proper implementation of the agreed terms, and to foster and promote the cultural, scientific, and technological development of the institutions involved.

In witness whereof, and for all appropriate purposes, the parties sign this document in a single copy and tenor, on the date indicated in the heading.

TWINNED

By Stars

Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs

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